

Recovering **metals** and **mineral fraction**
from steelmaking residues

Deliverable 2.2

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Abbreviations and acronyms

RDS	RecoDust slag
CZO	Crude Zinc Oxide
WP	Workpackage
BOFD	Basic oxygen furnace dust

Abstract

This document details the requirements of the RecoDust process in terms of both, input material specifications, and operational parameters. The following requirements are:

- Pneumatic conveying: moisture and grain size
- Smelting range: the melting point of the RecoDust slag (RDS) must be below about 1550°C
- Chemical composition: disruptive substances, like sulphur, must be limited since the RecoDust pilot plant is not designed for it

The operational parameters comprise the heat balance and the air excess ratio. The heat balance considers the heat of the under stoichiometric combustion, the chemical reactions, and the heat losses of the Flash-Reactor. The air excess ratio of the burner is between 0.7 and 0.9 in this area the process heat is provided as well as the required amount of reducing agents namely carbon monoxide and hydrogen.

1 Introduction

This document represents the requirements of the RecoDust process in terms of both, input material specifications, and operational parameters of the ReMFra project, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101058362.

The RecoDust process is a pyrometallurgical process for the treatment of steel mill dusts. Until now the feedstock was mainly basic oxygen furnace dust (BOFD). The BOFD used was fine dust, coarse dust, or mixtures of the two. Further tests with blast furnace sludge and electric arc furnace dusts round off the previous test programmes.

All the feedstocks containing zinc (1-20 wt.-%) and iron (~50 wt.-%) are separated in the RecoDust process into an iron rich fraction, the RecoDust slag (RDS), and a zinc rich fraction, the Crude Zinc Oxide (CZO).

Physical and chemical limits must be observed for both, the input material, and the process being described in the current document.

2 Requirements of the input material

The feedstock for the RecoDust process is filled into the pneumatic conveying storage tank. The pneumatic conveying should be performed with a uniform and stable dosing rate over the whole feeding time. The dust is transferred with natural gas as pneumatic conveying media directly into the flame of the Flash-Reactor, where it is slagged. The presence of liquid RDS is necessary for tapping. As a final point, the feedstock is subject to certain chemical composition requirements.

2.1 Pneumatic conveying requirements.

The pneumatic conveying system of the RecoDust pilot plant is shown in Figure 1. The system consists of the storage tank, the feeders of natural gas and nitrogen, the exhaust air, and the pneumatic conveying line to the burner.

The requirements for the feedstock are of a physical nature:

- dry (below 1 wt.-% moisture)
- grain size < 400 µm

The maximum grain size depends on the grain size distribution as tests with each feedstock provide crucial information on the pneumatic conveying ability.

Figure 1: Pneumatic conveying storage tank

2.2 Requirements of the smelting range

For the tapping of the RDS in the RecoDust process, it is necessary that the RDS is in a liquid state at the operating temperature. The temperature of the Flash-Reactor is limited by the maximum operating temperature of the refractory. The currently used refractory is a ramming mass based on Al_2O_3 and Cr_2O_3 with an application temperature limit of 1800°C . Therefore, the melting point of the RDS should be below 1550°C . In addition, the following must be considered:

- Higher Flash-Reactor temperatures lead to higher load and wear.
- Higher Flash-Reactor temperatures increase the specific energy demand of the RecoDust process.
- Higher Flash-Reactor temperatures lead to a higher dezincification rate of the feedstock.

Referring to these points, lower Flash-Reactor temperatures lead do a lower specific natural gas demand but may result in a lower dezincification.

2.3 Requirements of the chemical composition

The RecoDust pilot plant is designed for the use of BOFD with a ZnO content of 16.4 wt.-% and an iron content of 43.6 wt.-%. The exhaust line consists of the converter, the quench, and the bag filter.

The chemical analysis, chosen for the design of the RecoDust pilot plant, is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Chemical analysis of the feedstock for the design of the RecoDust pilot plant at the Chair of Thermal Processing Technology

Substance	Symbol	Amount [wt.-%]
Lead	Pb	0.3
Calcium oxide	CaO	13.6
Chlorine	Cl	0.3
Iron II	Fe II	13.6
Iron total	Fe _{tot.}	43.6
Metallic iron	Fe _{met.}	16.5
Fluorine	F	0.04
Potassium oxide	K ₂ O	0.4
Magnesium oxide	MgO	4.1
Sodium oxide	Na ₂ O	0.5
Sulphur	S	0.3
Silica	SiO ₂	1.7
Zinc	Zn	13.2

The content of sulphur in the feedstock is limited, as sulphuric acid would be formed in the exhaust gas line.

Other requirements should be discussed in view of the chemical composition of each feedstock, the range of used feedstocks used until now is shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Range of the chemical composition of the used RecoDust feedstocks so far

Substance	Symbol	Amount [wt.-%]
Lead	Pb	0 – 1
Calcium oxide	CaO	6 - 15
Chlorine	Cl	0 - 2
Iron total	Fe _{tot.}	40 - 60
Fluorine	F	0 – 0.2
Potassium oxide	K ₂ O	0 – 0.4
Magnesium oxide	MgO	1 – 5
Sodium oxide	Na ₂ O	0 – 0.4
Sulphur	S	0 – 0.7
Silica	SiO ₂	1 – 7.5
Zinc	Zn	0.9 – 35.5

Before the shipment to Austria, the chemical analysis of the feedstock must be submitted to the project partners Montanuniversität Leoben (MUL) and K1-MET. The following chemical elements and compounds must be listed: Zn, Al, Al₂O₃, As, Ba, Ca, CaO, Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Fe II, Fe III, Fe_{met.}, Fe_{tot.}, K₂O, Mg, MgO, Mn, MnO, Na, Na₂O, Ni, P, Pb, S, Sb, Se, SiO₂, Sn, V, W, Cl, F and Hg.

Finally, it must be declared, that no harmful substance is in the feedstock.

3 Requirements of the operational parameters

The operating requirements of the RecoDust process are one hand the heat balance, and the air excess ratio of the burner on the other hand. The used air excess ratio also must provide the necessary quantity of reducing agent.

3.1 Heat balance and cooling demand

One part of the operational parameters is the heat balance and the cooling demand. The heat balance is calculated via the Excel file "Variable balance", which was developed during the time period, when the RecoDust pilot plant development has started at the Chair of Thermal Processing Technology (MUL). This variable balance is flexible to the use of different kinds of feedstock, temperatures, and air excess ratios.

The variable balance uses the main chemical components as shown in Figure 2.

Input of the most important substances			
Compound	Analysis	Proportion	MG
	wt.-%	wt.-%	[g/mol]
CaO	8.45	9.55	56.08
MgO	1.57	1.77	40.33
SiO ₂	1.32	1.49	60.10
ZnO	11.6	13.11	81.39
Fe _{met.}	10.4	11.76	55.85
FeO	14.02	15.85	71.85
Fe ₂ O ₃	41.10	46.46	159.70
C	0	0.00	12.01
Total	88.467	100	
Correction factor	1.130		
Percentage dust	[wt.-%]		
Fe _{tot.}	50.05		
Fe _{met.}	10.4		
Fe II	10.9		
Fe _{rest}	28.750		
Fe ₂ O ₃	41.105		

Figure 2: Rough chemical composition for the variable balance used for the variable RecoDust balance model

The heat balance itself for the Flash-Reactor is calculated by:

- Combustion of natural gas and oxygen with an air excess ratio below 1
- Chemical reactions of the feedstock (reduction of Zn, oxidation of Fe_{met.}, reduction of hematite and so on)
- Heating energy of the feedstock
- Heat loss of the Flash-Reactor

The under stoichiometric combustion of natural gas and oxygen provides a reducing atmosphere and delivers the process heat. The combustion energy depends on the Flash-Reactor temperature and the air excess ratio. In Figure 3 the data of the enthalpy is shown.

Burning Energy of CH4 and O2 in dependence of Temperatur and air excess ratio							
[kJ/mol]							
	1500	1600	1700	1800	1900	tx	T0
0.7	313.9	299.9	285.9	271.8	257.6	-0.141	525
0.75	361.2	346.9	332.5	318.0	303.4	-0.145	578
0.8	408.8	394.1	379.3	364.4	349.4	-0.148	631
0.85	456.6	441.6	426.5	411.2	395.8	-0.152	685
0.9	504.7	489.4	473.9	458.2	442.3	-0.156	739
0.95	553.1	537.4	521.6	505.4	488.2	-0.162	797
1	599.9	582.2	563.3	542.6	519.7	-0.201	901
lx	953	941	925	903	874		
l0	-353	-359	-361	-360	-354		
H(T,L)= a +b*T + c*L				a	-101.1446		
				b	-0.152		
	288			c	924.6		

Figure 3: Enthalpy of combustion as a function of temperature and air excess ratio

The main chemical reaction of the feedstock is the endothermic reduction of zinc with CO or H₂.

The heating energy depends on the dosing rate of the feedstock and its chemical composition. The temperature dependence of the feedstock is considered, and the melting and evaporation enthalpies are added.

The radiation losses of the Flash-Reactor due to natural convection are also considered.

3.2 Air excess ratio and reduction

The air excess ratio of the natural gas/oxygen combustion as defined by the following chemical reaction, simplified with 100 % methane as fuel gas:

The simplified exhaust gas composition in dependence on the air excess ratio is shown in Figure 4. The operating region is between an air excess ratio of 0.7 and 0.9.

Figure 4: Exhaust gas composition of a methane oxygen combustion in dependence on the air excess ratio at 1700°C and the operating region of the RecoDust process

The quantity of reducing agents CO and H₂ must be matched with the quantity of ZnO of the feedstock.

In summary, there are opposing effects about dezincification and specific energy consumption:

- Higher air excess ratios result in lower specific energy consumption.

- The higher the zinc content in the feedstock, the lower the air excess ratio must be for a sufficient dezincification.